

IMI2 Project No 777372 - RESOLUTE

Research empowerment on solute carriers

WP8 – Knowledge integration and data management

D8.4 RESOLUTE knowledgebase

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¹ Document, report.

² Public, fully open.

Table of Contents

Publishable Summary.....	3
Introduction.....	3
Implementation.....	4
Backend architecture.....	5
Frontend architecture.....	5
Resources.....	5
Data mining workflows.....	6
Sustainability.....	7
Future development.....	7
Backend refactoring and development.....	7
Frontend refactoring and development.....	7
Feature requests procedure.....	7
Planned features.....	8
Dissemination.....	8
Appendix.....	8
Abbreviations.....	8

Publishable Summary

Membrane transporters represent 10% of the encoding human genome. The human transportome, the ensemble of transporters and their transported entities, deserves to be elucidated in its entirety and its interdependence. The more than 400 members of the Solute Carrier superfamily (SLC), arranged into 65 families based on sequence similarity, represent the largest group and a good place to start. Despite their involvement in disease and drug transport and efficacy, SLCs are severely understudied family of proteins. RESOLUTE's ambitious aim is to assign biochemical and biological functions to as many SLC genes as possible using systematic approach. To empower RESOLUTE with efficiently accessible state-of-art SLC knowledge, we developed the RESOLUTE knowledgebase. We compile and integrate information from multiple sources, allowing SLC researchers to rapidly get an overview on the current knowledge on any SLC transporter. The alpha release of the knowledgebase includes information on SLC at gene, transcript and protein level.

Introduction

The RESOLUTE web portal serves as an entry point to all RESOLUTE resources. It conveys our mission, introduces the consortium, has the latest news and offers the option of a newsletter subscription (Figure 1).

One section of the web portal is the RESOLUTE knowledgebase (Figure 2), which integrates publicly available data on members of the SLC families and associated drugs and ligands. An alpha version with limited functionality is already available since month 5 (i.e. Nov 2018). The public release of the beta version is planned for month 7 (i.e. Jan 2019).

The RESOLUTE web portal, and in particular the RESOLUTE knowledgebase is a database-driven web application. This report summarizes its implementation architecture, the current state of integrated resources and next steps planned.

Figure 1. RESOLUTE web portal.

Figure 2. Web interface to the alpha version of the RESOLUTE knowledgebase.

Implementation

The underlying hardware infrastructure is provided by the CeMM IT department. Employment of virtual machines allows for maximal flexibility and scalability. The RESOLUTE knowledgebase follows a client-server architecture, with the server (backend) managing a central database and serving requests from clients (frontend). So far, the web page is the only frontend. Additional frontends (e.g. a smartphone app) can build on the transparent API. The RESOLUTE knowledgebase is built on open-source software wherever possible. Figure 3 shows a simplified summary of the overall architecture.

Figure 3. Overview on RESOLUTE knowledgebase infrastructure and technology stack.

Backend architecture

For the backend architecture, we built on modern, but tested technologies. Application logic is running on a Node.js server (open source) and implemented in the TypeScript 3 language (open source). The data model is defined in classes, and we use TypeORM (open source) to map the model to the entity-relationship structure of the database. The actual database is served by a PostgreSQL (open source) instance. TypeORM also provides easy, object-oriented access to the database for the application. The frontend is provided a GraphQL (open source) API which is partially auto-generated by a PostGraphile (open source) instance. The use of Docker (open source) enables a frictionless deployment from the development server to the production server for updates on the application logic, the data access layer or the database server.

Authentication for accessing non-public areas of the RESOLUTE knowledgebase is provided by a Microsoft Azure Active Directory (via Office365), which is already employed by the consortium for communication and data sharing (see also Data Management Plan; deliverable 8.1).

Frontend architecture

The frontend is based on Vue.js (open source), a framework for component-based web user interfaces. We follow a *serverless* design, meaning that the client runs most of the application logic and the backend is only requested for specific services such as authentication or data queries. The Apollo GraphQL client (open source) is used for communication to the server.

Adhering to state-of-the-art web standards (HTML5, ES6, CSS3), the frontend is compatible to all modern web browsers. We test compatibility with Mozilla Firefox (open source) and with Google Chrome.

Resources

The RESOLUTE knowledgebase compiles information from multiple external databases and references to several resources (Table 1). We implemented different levels of integration of resources: “Linked” - link to the relevant web-page provided; “Integrated” - data from the resources are loaded into the local database; “API” - the most recent data is regularly downloaded using provided interfaces and loaded into the local database; “Widget” - data is visualized using embedded, third-party software modules.

To achieve high sustainability of the knowledgebase, we aim to integrate as many resources as possible using APIs if provided. This would allow to keep the database up-to-date almost automatically.

Table 1. Resources available in the RESOLUTE knowledgebase so far.

Resource name	Link	Current level of integration	Planned level of integration
HGNC	https://www.genenames.org	Integrated	API
ENSEMBL	https://www.ensembl.org	Integrated, Widget	API, Widget
NCBI/RefSeq	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/refseq/	Integrated	API
VEGA	http://vega.archive.ensembl.org	Linked	Linked
NCBI/Entrez	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gene/	Linked	Linked
neXtProt	https://www.nextprot.org/	Integrated, Widget	API, Widget
Protter	http://wlab.ethz.ch/protter/start/	Widget	Widget
BioGRID	https://thebiogrid.org	Linked	Linked
EBI/ChEMBL	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/chembl	Linked	Linked
GuideToPharmacology	http://www.guidetopharmacology.org	Linked	Linked
The Human Protein Atlas	https://www.proteinatlas.org	Linked	Linked
PDB	https://www.rcsb.org/	Linked	API
NCBI/Pubmed	https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/	Integrated	API

Data mining workflows

For collecting data from public resources, we either used R (open source) scripts or created re-usable workflows in KNIME (open source).

A KNIME workflow was developed to provide an overview of available information for the list of all SLCs. The data was collected from public databases via the Open PHACTS Discovery Platform Version 2.2. The user is provided with the counts of pharmacology information from ChEMBL, diseases from DisGeNET, pathways from Wikipathways and patents from SureChEMBL. A detailed list instead of the counts is also possible for single SLCs.

Following requests for data from other work packages (especially WP3), available public databases were analysed for integration within KNIME workflows. This data contains among others information on known substrates and co-substrates, cellular localization and potential assays.

As an example, the QuickGO workflow matches GO terms with SLCs. QuickGO is provided by the EBI and it is a browser for Gene Ontology data and annotations. GO terms are utilized representations in bioinformatics for genes and gene products. GO terms are classified into three aspects: molecular function, cellular component and biological process. Here, they were used to find possible substrates for SLCs, by joining the SLC table with GO terms containing transport reactions (Figure 4).

HGNC Approved Symbol	GO ID	Reaction	Substrates	Substrate_1	Substrate_2	Substrate_3	Notes
SLC1A1	GO:0015501	glutamate(out) + Na+(out) = glutamate(in) + Na+(in).	glutamate ; Na+	glutamate	Na+		symport
SLC1A1	GO:0015501	glutamate(out) + Na+(out) = glutamate(in) + Na+(in).	glutamate ; Na+	glutamate	Na+		symport
SLC1A1	GO:0015501	glutamate(out) + Na+(out) = glutamate(in) + Na+(in).	glutamate ; Na+	glutamate	Na+		symport
SLC1A2	GO:0015501	glutamate(out) + Na+(out) = glutamate(in) + Na+(in).	glutamate ; Na+	glutamate	Na+		symport
SLC1A2	GO:0015501	glutamate(out) + Na+(out) = glutamate(in) + Na+(in).	glutamate ; Na+	glutamate	Na+		symport
SLC1A3	GO:0015501	glutamate(out) + Na+(out) = glutamate(in) + Na+(in).	glutamate ; Na+	glutamate	Na+		symport
SLC1A3	GO:0015501	glutamate(out) + Na+(out) = glutamate(in) + Na+(in).	glutamate ; Na+	glutamate	Na+		symport

Figure 4. Part of the resulted table created via the QuickGO approach

These workflows are still under development and will be available soon to aid the generation of the next version of the priority list (deliverable D4.1).

While the workflows currently operate on downloaded data from different sources, integration of these workflows with public APIs and direct feedback of results to the RESOLUTE knowledgebase is planned. At the moment, KNIME workflows need to be run locally, but providing access via KNIME Server is currently under investigation.

Sustainability

The field of transmembrane transporter research is evolving rapidly, causing information compiled in any knowledgebase to inherently expire rather soon. Our solution to keep the RESOLUTE knowledgebase up-to-date as much as possible is to integrate most of the external resources and data through provided APIs. This implementation allows changes introduced to the external resources to be automatically synchronized to our knowledgebase in regular intervals.

CeMM commits to support and maintain the RESOLUTE knowledgebase during the whole period of RESOLUTE and 5 years after end of the grant, i.e. until mid of 2028.

Future development

The RESOLUTE knowledgebase integrates not only published, external resources and data, but will also include results produced and published within the RESOLUTE project. As we expect a significant amount of data generated over the next 5 years (see Data Management Plan; deliverable D8.1), flexibility and scalability of the infrastructure is key. We plan regular, major refactoring cycles taking place twice a year in order to adapt to new requirements arising from new data types or to resolve issues.

Backend refactoring and development

A first refactoring was already necessary at month 5, as we had to replace the data access layer (DAL) due to scalability issues. The initially employed software *Prisma* was replaced by a combination of *PostGraphile* and *TypeORM* which now serve as the interface to the PostgreSQL database, both for schema definition as well as CRUD operations.

Frontend refactoring and development

There have been no major refactoring cycles on the frontend development yet. For the next release, we plan to improve compatibility with Apple Safari and Microsoft Internet Explorer. Increased support for mobile devices is on the roadmap too.

Feature requests procedure

For now, new features for the RESOLUTE knowledgebase can be requested by any member of the RESOLUTE consortium. Requests will be reviewed and prioritized on regular base by the development team. A public forum for feedback is planned.

Planned features

The number of integrated resources will continue to grow throughout the project. Also, knowledge generated in the course of RESOLUTE will be made available and linked to existing knowledge.

The RESOLUTE knowledgebase should not only compile resources and data on SLCs but also allow the user to query and explore the increasing amount of data. To this end we will implement more and more interactive widgets and visualizations.

Dissemination

The RESOLUTE knowledgebase is openly accessible at the following URI: <https://re-solute.eu/knowledgebase>

To increase the visibility of the RESOLUTE knowledgebase, we plan to publish an article in a peer-reviewed, scientific journal. The choice of a journal should ensure high visibility for the relevant audience, i.e. SLC research community. Currently we are considering several possibilities for publication: (1) database issue of specialized journal, e.g. Nucleic Acid Research; (2) bioinformatic journal; (3) transporters focused journal.

Appendix

Abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
CRUD	Create, Read, Update and Delete
DAL	Data Access Layer
GO	Gene Ontology
RESOLUTE	Research Empowerment on Solute Carriers
SLC	Solute Carrier
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier